

Are Non-Topic Undergoers Direct Objects?: Evidence from Waray

Thomas E. Payne, University of Oregon and SIL International

Abstract: Waray is a major language spoken in the Eastern Visayas region of the Philippines. In this paper I argue that genitive case undergoers in clauses describing semantically transitive situations are neither direct objects, nor oblique constituents. Rather their grammatical properties result from speakers' choice to "de-perspectivize" an undergoer. Consequently, constructions that have been called "Actor-voice" in studies of other Philippine languages can be understood as grammatically Intransitive. This observation has profound consequences for the conceptualization of voice and grammatical relations in Philippine languages.

1. Introduction

Voice and case are extremely controversial topics in linguistic descriptions of Philippine languages. I will not summarize the many studies that have characterized this debate over the years. Rather my intent in this, hopefully brief, paper is to address one issue that seems to be key—namely the question of whether non-topic¹ undergoers are core arguments or not. If they are, then Philippine languages exhibit a rare or unique voice system in which there are two "symmetrical" transitive clause constructions, with the grammatical relations of the actor and the undergoer simply reversed. Pairs of examples similar to the following are often presented to show that the actors and undergoers may be expressed in the same grammatical case, depending on the morphology of the predicating word. These examples are in Waray, a Philippine language spoken by about three million people in the Eastern Visayas region of the Philippines:

- (1) a. *Ginhilot han nanay an batà.*
Gin-hilot **han nanay** an batà. Undergoer Voice (NOM = undergoer)
PAST.UV-massage GEN mother NOM child
'The mother massaged the child.'²

¹ Various terms have been used for the "topic" nominal in the clause structure of most Philippine languages, including pivot, focus, nominative, absolutive, subject, and probably others. This is a grammatical relation signalled by the pre-nominal markers *ang* or *si* in Tagalog full noun phrases. The Waray equivalents are *an* and *hi*. By "non-topic" I mean any nominal element that does not bear this grammatical relation.

² In this paper, the first line in Waray examples is the official Waray orthography, as described in Nolasco, Oyzon and Ramos (2012; revision of 2017 currently under consideration by the Department of Education). The second line provides morphological analyses, following the Leipzig formatting conventions (<https://www.eva.mpg.de/lingua/pdf/Glossing-Rules.pdf>). The third line gives the morpheme-by-morpheme glosses. Finally, the last line gives a free English translation.

References to the sources of examples are given in parentheses following the free translations. The primary published sources are the Corpora Project (2024), and Alunan (2016). The numbers in the Corpora Project references include the title of the text, and the sentence number within the text. Numbers in references to Alunan

b. *Naghilot an nanay han batà.*

Nag-hilot an nanay **han batà.** Actor Voice (NOM = actor)
PAST.AV-massage NOM mother GEN child
'The mother massaged the child.'

Such examples show, according to some linguists, that grammatical relations, signalled by the prenominal markers *an* and *han*, are reversed in these two transitive clauses. Therefore, these two constructions are equally as transitive, and neither one is derived from the other (see, e.g., Foley 1988, Kroeger 1993:47-48, Chen and McDonnell 2019:15, *inter alia*). The different prefixes on the verbs are the only indication of who is acting on whom (with constituent order serving a secondary function).

One major alternative to this view is that the pre-nominal case markers are multifunctional, with *han* in (1a) marking the ergative relation in a transitive clause, and *han* in (1b) marking a kind of oblique phrase in a grammatically intransitive clause. In this paper, I would like to argue for this alternative on three grounds: 1) multifunctionality is normal in language. The fact that two distinct grammatical categories overlap in form does not necessarily mean they have the same function. In fact, case syncretism between ergative and genitive cases is not uncommon in the world's languages. 2) The nominals represented by *han nanay* in (1a) and *han batà* in (1b) do not have the same syntactic properties. In particular, they pronominalize differently and have different distributional properties. 3) The history and typology of most Philippine languages lends itself to the kind multifunctionality I am claiming for *han* (and the other manifestations of "genitive" case). This typology is very different from that of languages most linguists are familiar with, and therefore has been challenging for many to comprehend.

2. Multifunctionality and genitive/ergative case syncretism

Multifunctionality in language is normal. In particular case syncretism (also known as isomorphism—'same form') is normal. Examples abound in which core and non-core cases overlap or are identical in form. In a typological study of case syncretism, Baerman and Brown

(2016) refer to the page number. Examples with no parenthesized references are from native speaker intuition or conversations. Each of these examples has been verified by at least two native speakers.

In the current official orthography, syllable prominence (either word stress, vowel length, or both) is not indicated when it is predictable. When it is unpredictable given the context, an acute accent indicates syllable prominence. Briefly, if the final syllable is prominent, no accent is needed. If there is a "heavy" syllable (CVC, or CV:) anywhere in the word other than the last syllable, the prominence predictably moves to the left, and so is not indicated. All other prominent syllables in indigenous Waray words are indicated with an acute accent. In Spanish and English loan words, stress is not indicated at all. Syllable prominence alone may distinguish lexical items. In addition, several morphological distinctions involve changes in syllable prominence patterns. The glottal stop is a full, phonemic consonant, and is indicated in one of five ways: 1) words written with an initial vowel grapheme always begin with a glottal stop, e.g. *anak* [ʔan'ak] 'offspring'; 2) Sequences of vowel graphemes always involve an intervening glottal stop, e.g., *tiil* [ti'ʔil], 'foot', *baò* [ba'ʔo] 'tortoise'; 3) Following a consonant, the glottal stop is indicated with a hyphen, e.g. *mag-áanak* [mag'ʔaʔanak] 'will give birth' 4) At the end of a word in a prominent syllable, it is indicated with a circumflex over the final vowel, e.g., *kitâ* [ki'taʔ] 'to see'; 5) At the end of a word in a non-prominent syllable, it is indicated with a grave accent over the final vowel, e.g., *sikò* ['si:koʔ] 'elbow'. In such cases the penultimate syllable is predictably prominent. Most published material in Waray does not follow the official standard, and simply omits diacritics entirely.

(2013) found that case syncretism was present in 40 of 73 languages they investigated that involved morphological case marking. They also mention Central Yup'ik as one language in which ergative and genitive cases are completely syncretic. To this we may add Mayan languages such as Ixil (Townsend 1986), and North American languages such as Nez Perce (Rude 1991). Therefore the fact of case-syncretism illustrated in (1), while consistent with the symmetrical voice hypothesis, is not prima-facie evidence in favor of it.

3. Grammatical properties of genitive undergoers

Genitive marked undergoers in Waray (*han bata* in 1b above) do not have syntactic properties of core arguments. In this section I will illustrate four ways in which they differ in syntactic properties from ergative actors. These differences involve pronominalization, omissibility, movement and syntactic “control”.

3.1. Pronominalization

The examples in (1) illustrate sentences with full noun phrase actor and undergoer. When these elements are pronominalized, however, the difference between the ergative and genitive cases begin to emerge. Ergative referring expressions may be replaced by the ergative/genitive pronouns, e.g., *niya* in (2)a, whereas undergoers in constructions such as (2)b may not (glosses in the following Waray examples reflect the alternative analysis advanced in this paper):

- (2) a. *Ginhiilot niya an bata.*
g<in>-hiilot niya an batâ.
 DEL<TR.R>-massage 3SG.ERG ABS.CONS child
 ‘S/he massaged the child.’
- b. *Naghiilot an nánay niya.*
na-g-hiilot an nánay niya
 INTR.NEU-DEL-massage ABS.CONS mother 3SG.GEN
 ‘Her/his mother massaged (someone).’
- c. **Naghiilot niya an nanay.*

Example (2)b is perfectly grammatical, but the pronoun *niya* must be understood as an adnominal possessor of *nanay* ‘mother’. It may not refer to the undergoer of the massage. The ungrammatical example (2)c also shows that *niya* may not refer to the undergoer, even if it is placed immediately after the verb.

Non-topic undergoers may be pronominalized, but not with the dedicated ergative/genitive pronouns. Rather an oblique form must be used:

- (3) *Naghiilot an nánay ha iya.*
na-g-hiilot an nánay ha iya
 INTR.NEU-DEL-massage ABS.CONS mother OBL 3SG.OBL
 ‘The mother massaged him/her.’ (Less forcefully, without much effort, or improperly)

Such constructions illustrate at least two facts not often brought to light in descriptions of Philippine voice system. Most relevant for the claims of this paper is that non-topic undergoers (*ha iya* in example (3)) are overtly marked as oblique rather than genitive when pronominalized. This is evidence that they are not direct objects. Secondly, such examples show that non-topic undergoers need not be “indefinite,” since pronouns necessarily refer to participants the speaker judges as identifiable. When occurring as full noun phrases, non-topic undergoers often are non-specific, generic or incompletely affected, but this is only one manifestation of the more general function of such “actor voice” constructions. As argued in Payne and Oyzon (2023, 2024), the overarching function of these constructions is to reduce, or “mitigate” scalar transitivity. Example (3) expresses the idea that the massage was less than effective for one reason or another. Reduced effectiveness is one component of scalar transitivity, as observed in Hopper and Thompson (1980) and reiterated in Næss (2007) among others. This reduction in semantic transitivity motivates the use of an overtly marked grammatically Intransitive construction.

One fact not often highlighted in studies that argue for or assume the symmetrical voice hypothesis is that the AV verb forms (examples 1b, 2b and (3)) are the forms used for unquestionably intransitive situations. The roots illustrated below may only occur with Intransitive verbal inflection, unless a special transitive sense is intended, or valence increasing morphology (causative or applicative) is used (see Payne and Oyzon 2023, 2024 for further details and argumentation):

(4) a. *Tumawa hiya.*

t<um>awa hiya
 <INTR.R>smile 3SG.ABS
 ‘S/he smiled.’

b. *Tumawa an batà.*

t<um>awa an batà
 <INTR.R>smile ABS.CONS child
 ‘The child smiled.’

(5) a. *Nagsayaw hi Lillia ha entablado.*

na-g-sayaw hi Lillia ha entablado
 INTR.NEU.R-DEL-dance ABS.PERS Lillia LOC stage
 ‘Lillia danced on stage.’ (A particular, deliberate act).

b. *Sumayaw hi Lillia ha entablado.*

s<um>ayaw hi Lillia ha entablado
 <INTR.CTRL>dance ABS.PERS Lillia LOC stage
 ‘Lillia (normally) dances on stage.’ / ‘Lillia danced (as expected) (on stage).’

c. *Magsasayaw hi Lillia ha entablado.*

ma-g-sa~sayaw hi Lillia ha entablado
 <INTR.NEU. IR>-DEL-RED1-dance ABS.PERS Lillia LOC stage
 ‘Lillia will dance on stage.’

Other verbs that fall into this class include *tindog* ‘stand’, *lakat* ‘walk’, *langoy* ‘swim’, *lukso* ‘jump’, *turog* ‘sleep’, *luhod* ‘kneel’ and many others. The conclusion is that the verb affixes (including *mag-*, *nag-* and *<um>* illustrated here) are overt markers of grammatical Intransitivity. If a semantically transitive situation is intended, the contrasting Transitive set of affixes (including *gin-* illustrated in 1a and 2a) must be used, often with accompanying valence increasing morphology in the verb stem.

From this point of view, AV constructions such as (1)b and (2)b are overtly marked as grammatically intransitive. They express semantically transitive situations, but in grammatically Intransitive forms.³ In this respect they are similar to such English expressions as *Irving already ate*, *I saw*, *I conquered*, *She ate pizza*, or *She chewed on the bone*. These are all semantically transitive in that they describe activity that carries over from an actor to an undergoer, but they are presented by the speaker as grammatically Intransitive in some way, either by omitting reference to the undergoer altogether, or treating it as less definite, less specific or less completely affected by the activity of the predicate. They are more about what the actor *does*, than what happens to some undergoer. In section 4 I will have more to say about the typological differences between English and Waray that lead to the two languages treating such functionally similar constructions differently.

3.2. Omissability of the de-perspectivized undergoer

It has been claimed (e.g. by Chen and McDonnell 2019:15) that the undergoer in Actor Voice (AV) constructions must be a core argument in Tagalog because it cannot be omitted. This is false for Tagalog and for Waray. Most “semantically transitive” predicates may appear in an AV construction with no reference to an undergoer. Here are a few of the many examples that appear in the Waray corpus:

- (6) *Nag-iininaw ngay-an hira, diri pa ngay-an nira igarawas hito nga oras.*
na-g-i~ <in>inaw ngay-an hira diri pa ngay-an nira
 INTR.R-DEL-INCMPL-REP-watch yet 3PL.ABS NEG CONT yet 3PL.ERG
- i-g-g<ar>awas hito nga oras*
 APPL2-DEL-DIST-flow.out DEMO2.ABS LK time

‘They were just observing, (but) it was not yet time for them to go out.’ (Alunan 2016: 3)

³ In order to highlight the important distinction between semantic and grammatical transitivity, I will capitalize terms referring to grammatical Transitivity and not capitalize terms referring to semantic transitivity.

- (7) *Di, pumakiana hira kun ano daw la adi.*
di p<um>akiana hira kun ano daw la adi.
 then⁴ <INTR.R.CTRL>ask 3PL.ABS if what HSY CMPL DEMO3.ABS
 ‘They asked (of themselves), what this could be.’ (Alunan 2016: 4)

Examples (6) and (7) both illustrate semantically transitive roots in grammatically intransitive frames with no genitive marked undergoer. Both of these verbs, like most semantically transitive roots, fall into a class of roots which Payne and Oyzon (2020) call “agent-preserving labile roots”. Example (7) illustrates one common usage of the <um> ‘intransitive, realis, controlled modality’ infix. The default interpretation in this case is that the absolutive case actors (*hira*) ask themselves or one another, even though there is no reflexive nominal, or reciprocal marking on the verb that would enforce either of these interpretations.

In Waray and in Tagalog, there are some semantically transitive roots that do seem, at least out of context, to require overt expression of the undergoer in an AV construction. However, it must be pointed out that such apparent non-omissability of elements does not automatically indicate those elements are direct objects—there are such things as “obligatory obliques”. Consider such English clauses as *I went to your office*, and *Put the book on the table*. While a string like *I went* may be understood as a complete fully grammatical clause, it still seems to require a destination, which may only be expressed as an oblique or locational noun (e.g., *I went home*). Perhaps even clearer is the second example, in which the string **Put the book* is more unambiguously ungrammatical without an obligatory location expressed as an oblique.

3.3. Fronting of de-perspectivized undergoers

It has been claimed for Tagalog (e.g., by Kroeger 1993: 47) that the genitive-marked undergoer in a de-transitive construction is not an oblique argument because it cannot occur in front of the verb in the way obliques can: “(In Tagalog) genitive marked patients can never undergo Adjunct Fronting . . . This implies that they are terms, i.e., Objects, since any non-term can appear in this construction” (Kroeger 1993: 47). While the empirical observation is correct—obliques are often fronted and genitive marked undergoers are not—the conclusion that genitive undergoers are therefore core arguments (direct objects) does not follow. In fact core arguments certainly do occur in preverbal position, in Tagalog and in Waray. In particular, absolutives serving any semantic role are the most likely clause elements to appear before the verb in both Tagalog and Waray—and absolutives are certainly core arguments (or “terms”). Ergatives may also appear before the verb when pronominalized. Therefore, the fact that genitive undergoers do not naturally occur before the verb sets them apart from both “core arguments” (e.g., absolutives and ergatives) and obliques.

⁴ Speakers often use the contracted form of the irrealis negative marker *diri* as a discourse connector. In this context, the best gloss is ‘then’—it does not negate the following clause.

The following are some Waray examples from the corpus showing that absolutes and ergatives may occur before the verb. Example (8) illustrates an absolutive actor in preverbal position (in this example and the following, the fronted elements are bolded).

(8) ***Ini hi** Nanay nagpípinamulod.*

Ini hi Nánay na-[g-pí~p<in>a-m-ulod]

DEMO.ABS ABS.PERS Mom INTR.R-DEL-INCMPL-<REP>-INF-PLC-cut.tree

‘As for Mom, she was going around cutting down trees.’ (Alunan 2016: 72)

Example (9) illustrates a fronted absolutive undergoer, while example (10) illustrates a fronted ergative pronoun:

(9) ***An mga batô** pinas-an níya.*

an mga batô p<in>inas-an níya

ABS.CONC PL stone <TR.R>carry.on.shoulder-APPL1 3SG.ERG

‘The stones he carried on his shoulders.’ (Alunan 2016: 209)

(10) Translation of previous sentence: ‘I stood up hurriedly and wiped the table.’

***Akon** ginkuha an pinggan ngan ginbutang didto han ligid han lamesa kun diin ako nalingkod.*

akon g<in>kuha an pinggan ngan g<in>butang didto han ligid han

1SG.ERG DEL<T.R>get ABS.CONC dish and DEL<TR.R>put there GEN.DEF edge GEN.DEF

lamesa kun diin ako na-lingkod

table if where 1SG.ABS R.HAP-sit

‘I took the plate and put it near the edge of the table where I happened to be sitting.’

(Corpora Project 2024: Essay by Carol Anne Aballar 75)

These examples show that indeed core arguments may be fronted in Waray. I understand that the same is true in Tagalog as well. If genitive marked undergoers in de-transitive constructions were core arguments, we would expect that they could be fronted as well. However, as Kroeger observes for Tagalog, this is not the case:

(11) **?Hin surat nagsurat an babáyi.*

hin surat na-g-surat an babáyi

GEN.INDEF letter INTR.R-DEL-write ABS.CONC woman

(‘A letter the woman wrote.’)

(12) **?Han batà naghilot an babáyi.*

han batà na-g-hilot an babáyi

GEN.DEF child INTR.R-DEL-massage ABS.CONC woman

(‘The child the woman massaged.’)

(13) **?Ha iya naghilot an babáyi.*

ha iya batà na-g-hilot an babáyi
 OBL 3SG.OBL child INTR.R-DEL-massage ABS.CONS woman
 ('Her/him the woman massaged.')

These sentences are interpretable but are described as poetic or “Yoda speech” by native Waray speakers. No examples of fronted genitive or oblique marked undergoers have been found in the corpus. Part of the reason for this prohibition against fronted preverbal non-topic undergoers is that they do not pronominalize in the same way as ergatives do (see section 3.1), and ergatives must be pronominalized in order to occur preverbally (see ex. (10)). Pre-predicate arguments are contrastive, and therefore tend to be identifiable, given, and referential. Since genitive undergoers are normally non-referential or otherwise “de-perspectivized,” their pragmatic functions tend to be incompatible with pre-predicate position. The conclusion is that undergoers in de-transitive constructions are neither core arguments nor prototypical obliques.

These facts illustrate that “oblique” in Waray is not necessarily a unitary category. In fact, some linguistic theories posit multiple types of obliques. For example, Role and Reference Grammar (Van Valin 2001) proposes a distinction between “core obliques” vs. “peripheral obliques.” Relational grammar (Perlmutter 1980) famously introduced the concept of “chômeur” as a label for a nominal relation that has syntactic properties of neither “terms” (core arguments) nor obliques. While I do not take a stand on either of these theoretical frameworks, I believe these frameworks provide some insight into the status of genitive-marked undergoers in Waray. Genitive-marked undergoers are in a pragmatically “de-perspectivized” grammatical role, and as such lack some syntactic properties of core arguments (ergatives and absolutes) while simultaneously lacking some syntactic properties of obliques.

3.4. “Control” in participial adjunct constructions

Finally, it has been claimed beginning with Kroeger 1993 that genitive undergoers must be core arguments (direct objects) because they control coreference in certain clause combining constructions in Tagalog. The following examples illustrate this claim (glosses and formatting conventions are those given in Kroeger 1993: 47).

Tagalog:
 (14) *Hinuli ng polis ang magnanakaw*
h<in>uli ng polis ang magnanakaw
 PERF-catch-OV GEN police NOM thief

nang pumapasok sa bangko.
nang p<um>a~pasok sa bangko
 ADV <AV>IMPERF~enter DAT bank

‘The police caught the thief entering the bank.’

The question is, which of the two participants mentioned in the first clause of (14) is understood as the participant entering the bank in the second clause. In this example with “Object Voice” (Transitive) marking on the first verb, either the police or the thief may be understood as the

participant entering the bank. Example (15) illustrates a similar sequence, but with “Actor Voice” (Intransitive) marking on the first verb and the thief appearing in the genitive case.

Tagalog:

(15) *Nanghuli ng magnanakaw ang polis*
nang-huli ng magnanakaw ang polis
AV.PERF-catch GEN thief NOM police

nang pumapasok sa bangko.
nang p<um>a~pasok sa bangko
ADV <AV>IMPERF~enter DAT bank

‘The police caught the thief entering the bank.’

In this example, again, it may be understood that the event expressed in the first clause happened while either the police or the thief were entering the bank. The conclusion is that the thief, even though expressed as a genitive marked undergoer of the first clause, may still control coreference of the actor of the second clause, and therefore must be a core argument.

The main problem with these examples is that they are not natural. They are obviously elicited, rather than from a Tagalog conversation or text, therefore the coreference relationships are unclear. In particular, the first clause of example (15) implies that there is no particular thief the police caught. As observed by one Tagalog consultant, it is as though the police were out “thief catching.” Another mentioned that it was like the police were “catching fish in a tank”, as though some thief were there among many others specifically to be caught. The second clause presents a conflicting scene in that it implies some specific person entered the bank, probably the police, but it could be anyone, including possibly some thief. It all depends on the context in which this story is being told.

My observation for Tagalog and for similar examples in Waray is that these are not “control” constructions at all. The syntax of the main clause in combination with the second clause neither requires nor precludes coreference between any of the participants. Rather coreference or lack thereof is inferred via the roles and pragmatic statuses of the various participants in the discourse context.

In summary, all four of the major arguments that purport to show that genitive marked undergoers in de-transitive constructions are in fact direct objects are based on faulty data or reasoning. Unfortunately similar data and arguments have resurfaced in several publications in the past thirty years (e.g., Chen and McDonnell 2019, Hemmings 2021, *inter alia*), thus possibly giving the impression that the “symmetrical voice” hypothesis is established fact.

The more consistent analysis is that semantically transitive AV constructions are in fact grammatically Intransitive. They constitute a way of downplaying the semantic centrality of the undergoer, according to the perspective of the speaker. Because Waray verbal predicates are overtly marked for Transitivity, this very useful communicative function is elegantly achieved by

Intransitive syntax and verbal inflection. No new typological category of “symmetrical voice” systems or languages is necessary.

4. The typology of Philippine languages

I have not investigated all the languages of the world, but I would guess that all languages include constructions that in one way or another allow speakers to de-perspectivize the undergoer in a transitive situation. In this section I would like to observe that the morphosyntactic typology of Waray lends itself to expressing such de-perspectivization by overt marking of the verb. Whether or not it is universal, de-perspectivization of an undergoer by de-transitivization is certainly common. Simple examples from English have already been given. Here they are again, with some additions:

- (16)a. Irving already ate.
- b. I saw, I conquered.
- c. She ate pizza.
- d. She chewed on the bone.
- e. Maradona kicks!
- f. Micah shaved.
- g. John and Mary embraced.
- h. Romeo drank of the potion.

In English all of these might be considered “semantically transitive” situations, that is to say they describe situations that inherently involve activity “transferring over” from a conscious initiator to some undergoer. These transitive situations are expressed in grammatically Intransitive constructions with the undergoer de-perspectivized in some way. Possible corresponding grammatically Transitive constructions would be:

- (17)a. Irving already ate his lunch.
- b. I saw Zela, I conquered Zela.
- c. She ate my pizza.
- d. She chewed the bone.
- e. Maradona kicks the ball!
- f. Micah shaved himself.
- g. John and Mary embraced each other.
- h. Romeo drank the potion.

In English, as in many languages linguists are familiar with, de-transitivization as in (16) is mostly accomplished in the expression of the undergoer, either by eliminating it entirely (16)a, b, e, f, and g, expressing it as generic (16)c, or by placing it in an oblique role (16)d and h. The verb forms in all the grammatically Intransitive constructions in (16) and the corresponding grammatically Transitive constructions in (17) remain the same, no matter whether or how the undergoer is expressed.

However, in Waray, constructions corresponding to (16) would all have to occur with Intransitive verbal morphology (as illustrated in examples (4) through (8) above), whereas those

corresponding to (17) would occur in a transitive form. This is consistent with the general typology of most Philippine languages in that much of the functional “work” of indicating the relationship between semantic roles and grammatical relations is accomplished in the verb. Verbs in most Philippine languages tend to be polysynthetic, while noun phrases tend to be much more analytic, with case, number and some pragmatic statuses similar to definiteness or specificity being expressed analytically, rather than morphologically.

There are also typically only three cases in a Philippine language: Absolutive, ergative/genitive and oblique. Therefore, as observed earlier, multifunctionality of case forms is very common. In particular, in addition to marking ergative and genitive NPs, the full NP ergative/genitive case also serves to mark de-perspectivized undergoers. In contrast, there are many verb forms that express the grammatical relations of the various NPs in a clause. These include Transitive/Intransitive inflection, causatives, and applicatives (see, e.g., Payne and Oyzon 2022 and 2024). More of this functional work is accomplished in the verb rather than the nominal elements in a clause.

5. Conclusion

In this paper I have addressed one part of the controversy over “voice” in Philippine languages. Many questions still remain, but these are well covered elsewhere (see e.g. Payne and Oyzon 2020, 2022, 2023, and Oyzon and Payne in preparation). The main assertion of the present paper is that genitive marked undergoers in Actor Voice constructions are not core arguments (i.e., direct objects), as has been claimed in much of the previous literature, principally works that claim that Philippine languages (usually Tagalog) embody a rare or unique voice system. While Philippine languages are indeed unique and special in many ways, there is no need to posit a typologically rare or unique “Philippine type” voice system.

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